

The method and arrangement of teaching foreign languages

Rahmonberdi Yuldashev,

4-rd year student, NUUZ

Annotation: This article deals with the education, which is like almost every other area of our society, has evolved in leaps and bounds in recent years. This article also analyses the traditional teaching techniques, based mainly on a teacher explaining a topic and students taking notes that may still be useful on occasion. The education, which today revolves more around encouraging the student to awaken their curiosity and desire to learn.

Key words: method, language, education, knowledge, drills, brainstorming

Аннотация: Ушбу мақола жамиятимизнинг деярли барча соҳалари каби сўнги йилларда ўта ривожланган таълимга бағишланган. Ушбу мақолада анъанавий ўқитиш усуллари таҳлил қилинади, асосан ўқитувчи мавзунини тушунтириб бериши ва ўқувчилар вақти-вақти билан фойдали бўлиши мумкин бўлган эслатмаларга асосланади. Бугунги кунда кўпроқ ўқувчининг қизиқиши ва ўрганиш истагини уйғотишга қаратилган таълим.

Калит сўзлар: усул, тил, таълим, билим, машқлар, ақлий ҳужум

Аннотация: В этой статье речь идет об образовании, которое, как и почти любая другая сфера нашего общества, развивалось стремительными темпами в последние годы. В этой статье также анализируются традиционные методы обучения, основанные главным образом на том, что учитель объясняет тему, а учащиеся делают заметки, которые иногда могут быть полезны. Образование, которое сегодня больше вращается вокруг поощрения учащихся к пробуждению их любопытства и желания учиться.

Ключевые слова: метод, язык, образование, знания, упражнения, мозговой штурм.

Introduction: Although a large proportion of the world's population speaks two or more languages, the studying of foreign language learning is not commonplace, thus, few students ever have the opportunity to avail themselves of such knowledge. Almost everyone has been studied a second language at some time in their schooling, but only a few learners have developed a specialized interest in learning and teaching a second language.

First of all, we should create some rules in teaching for ourselves. For example, we should use of shortcuts to keep the pace or drills and use normal a language stress,

intonation and juncture patterns conscientiously. Drill material should always be meaningful. If the content words are not known, you should teach their meanings. We should be friendly with students. The teacher should design projects that are appropriate for their students, taking into account their age and knowledge, while making them attractive enough to provide extra motivation. Every human's psychology is differently, therefore they can learn the foreign languages differently. And there are a lot of different methods of teaching and learning. According to these methods we should divide the learners into groups. Through the dividing we can teach and attract the learners. Because all of them prefer different methods, therefore, they can learn the languages.

The first method is "Design Thinking" method. It is also called "Case Method". This technique is based on resolving real-life cases through group analyses, brainstorming, innovation and creative ideas. Although "Design Thinking" is a structured method, in practice it can be quite messy as some cases may have no possible solution. However, the Case Method prepares students for the real world and arouses their curiosity, analytical skills and creativity. This technique is often used in popular MBA or Masters classes to analyze real cases experienced by companies in the past.

The second method is "Grammar Translation", written literary texts. Translate from your first language into the second language. It consisted mainly of exhaustive use of dictionaries, explanations of grammatical rules (in English), some sample sentences, and exercise drills to practice the new structures. Little opportunity for real second-language acquisition existed.

The third method is "Audio – Lingual", with the advent and popularity of audio tapes, this method ushered in the first recordings where in the language learner could actually hear and mimic native speakers on reel-to-reel audio tapes, often used with earphones in a language lab setting. Lessons often began with a sample dialogue to be recited and memorized. This was followed up with substitution pattern and saturation drills in which the grammatical structure previously introduced was reinforced, with emphasis given to rapid fire student response. Repetition, substitution, transformation, and translation became the order of the day. This method was strongly influenced by B.F. Skinner's behaviorist view toward learning which favored habit-forming drill techniques. Unfortunately, most students couldn't transfer these dialogues into their own real-life experiences.

The fourth method is the "Direct Method". This method presented discussion in the target language as the major priority. Reference to English equivalents became discouraged. Grammar learning became inductive in nature without overt

explanations given the pupil. Teacher or student interaction became fuller, guessing of context or content, completing fill-ins, and doing “cloze” exercises were the order of the day. Accuracy in pronunciation and oral expression became vital. Examples to be followed became the main intention.

The teaching of foreign language may take place as a general school subject or in a specialized school. There are many methods of teaching languages. Some have fallen into relative obscurity and others are widely used: still others have a small following but offer useful insights. A teaching method comprises the principles and methods used for instruction. Commonly used teaching methods may include students or listeners participation, demonstration, recitation or combinations of these. The choice of an appropriate teaching method depends largely on the information or skill that is being taught, it may also be influenced by the aptitude and enthusiasm of the students. For effective teaching to take place, a good method must be adopted by a teacher. A teacher has many options when choosing a style by which to teach. The teacher may write lesson plans of their own, borrow plans from other teachers, search online or within books for lesson plans.

The effectiveness of teaching method varies from person to person and also from activity to activity. Teaching by making students do, read, listen all have the transfer of information as their goal, but the information is transferred in very different ways in each case. Each has its own benefits. In my own opinion, teaching by letting students do is the method that works best for me. Teaching by making students do works because it gives a learner first-hand experience. Other methods are more passive, you are either listening to a conversation or trying to pay attention to words on a page. However, teaching by making students do means actually participating in the activity. Can you imagine teaching how to play a musical instrument from a book? As the saying goes, practice makes perfect. Frankly, I can't think of a way that better ensures one has truly learned than by seeing and doing. In contrast, reading makes learning less easy to visualize. Not only has that, learning by reading often required extra research, such as looking up unfamiliar words. Also, you might not be a good reader, or you might be teaching in a second language. If so, you might find it hard to concentrate or become frustrated by the slow pace. So while reading is fun and useful for many people, for others it may not be the best way. Teaching by listening can be enjoyable. Lively debate is interesting, and interesting things are usually easier to learn about. Plus, unlike reading, you can ask questions to check whether students understand or not what you mean. However, as with reading, it is all too easy to become a passive listener and not truly learn anything. If students get bored they might even fall asleep while they are listening. When

students are actively participating in something, they are more likely to stay alert. Having students work in groups is another way a teacher can direct a lesson. Collaborating allows students to talk with each other and listen to all points of view in the discussion. It helps students to think in a less personally based way. When this lesson plan is carried out the teacher may be trying to assess the lesson by looking at the students' ability to work as team, leadership skills, or presentation abilities. It is one of the direct instructional methods. A different kind of group work is the discussion.

Conclusion: The fifth method is “Learning by teaching”, is a widespread method in Germany, developed by Jean- Pol. Martin. The students take the teacher's role and teach their peers. Over the teaching they can repeat and over the repeating they can fortify their knowledge.

Of course, these methods help us in teaching and learning. Every methods have own roles in our life. But we must know when or how use from these methods

Reference:

1. To read more on Situational Language Teaching and other methods
2. Richards, J. C. & Rogers, T. S. (1986). Approaches and methods in language teaching: A description and analysis. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press
3. Khodjamkulov, U., Makhmudov, K., & Shofkorov, A. (2020). The Issue of Spiritual and Patriotic Education of Young Generation in the Scientific, Political and Literary Heritage of Central Asian Thinkers. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 24(05), 6694-6701.
4. Yuldashev R.Sh-Yoshlarda xorijiy tilda bilm va konikmalarini shakllantirish. Innovative developments and research in education international scientific-online conference part 10 r October, 2022 - Canada, Ottawa